

Phosphorus, eutrophication and the importance of scales: a place-based transdisciplinary analysis of scalar dynamics

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Abstract

Phosphorus-driven eutrophication of surface waters persists across Europe and Water Framework Directive (WFD) implementation is slow. Calls for better management approaches advocate for involving multiple stakeholders, considering social, ecological and technological drivers, and applying ‘multi-level’ or ‘multi-scalar’ approaches. However, multi-level approaches rarely apply ‘scales’ and ‘levels’ drawn from the experiences of stakeholders engaged in management efforts, or systematically explore these multi-dimensional drivers. This may limit understandings of how the interplay of scales and levels affects mitigation efforts. To address this limitation, we conducted a place-based transdisciplinary case study, centred around Stockholm (Sweden), to elaborate how sociopolitical and hydrological scales became important during efforts to address eutrophication. Misalignments between sociopolitical drivers across levels, including policy goals, legislation, funding and norms, were found to inhibit the prioritisation and implementation of WFD goals at city, sub-catchment and micro levels. Furthermore, cross-scalar misalignments inhibited actions across relevant sociopolitical levels that were sensitive to drivers across the hydrological scale. Legislation around water and land-use restricted planning according to sub-catchment level dynamics, while knowledge of hydrological drivers at the sub-catchment and micro-level were seen as inadequate to support strategy development or their funding and implementation. Greater efforts are needed to understand and address these misalignments to enable successful phosphorus management, where multiple goals co-exist and must be implemented simultaneously. Enhanced cross-level collaboration may act as

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an essential enabler by facilitating ‘buy-in’, enhancing knowledge of hydrological drivers at the sub-catchment and micro levels, and improving their integration into decision-making across sociopolitical levels.

Keywords: Sustainability; socio-ecological systems; Water Framework Directive; multi-level; multi-scalar; urban agriculture

1. Introduction

Despite decades of research and policy interventions, eutrophication remains a central reason for the failure of 60% of EU surface waters to reach good ecological status as defined by the Water Framework Directive (WFD) (Directive 2000/60/EC Establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy, 2000; European Environmental Agency, 2018). Phosphorus over-enrichment is a key driver of eutrophication (Correll, 1999); therefore, mitigating phosphorus losses is essential to address this ‘wicked problem’ (Jacobs *et al.*, 2017; Head, 2022; Martin-Ortega *et al.*, 2022). Like all ‘wicked problems’ eutrophication is intractable, multifaceted and involves multiple actors (Head, 2022), which has driven a turn towards transdisciplinary approaches (Duckett *et al.*, 2016). These approaches focus on multi-actor participation, from consultation to (ideally) the full co-development of solutions, and approach problems as emergent properties of systems that consist of interacting ecological, technological and social elements (Mauser *et al.*, 2013; Lam *et al.*, 2021). Transdisciplinary approaches can therefore identify and enable action on ‘deep’ leverage points for system transformation (Abson *et al.*, 2017) through developing ‘socially robust’ solutions that have high actor buy-in (Lang *et al.*, 2012a; Balvanera *et al.*, 2017; Lam *et al.*, 2021).

An emerging question is how to deal with issues of scale when applying transdisciplinary approaches (Buizer, Arts and Kok, 2011). The phosphorus challenge, like many other sustainability problems, is characterised as one that must be addressed across multiple scales and levels (Cordell, Neset and Prior, 2012; Metson *et al.*, 2015; Withers *et al.*, 2015). This is an important challenge when integrating knowledge from multiple academic disciplines and non-academic actors (Lang *et al.*, 2012), who conceptualise and use scales in diverse ways (Gibson, Ostrom and Ahn, 2000; Cash *et al.*, 2006; Vervoort *et al.*, 2012). In the literature, terms like ‘scale’ and ‘level’ are often used interchangeably, however, they are conceptually different (Gibson, Ostrom and Ahn, 2000; Cash *et al.*, 2006; Vervoort *et al.*, 2012). In this study, we draw on the conceptual understanding outlined by Vervoort *et al.*, (2012), to define a scale as a conceptual framework that is used to structure analysis of objects of study according to certain dimensions (e.g time, space, power or interconnectedness), which may be used alone or in some combination to define a scale. Levels within a scale are then used to demarcate where there is expected to be a significant change in observed characteristics (Gibson, Ostrom and Ahn, 2000). (Vervoort *et al.*, 2012).

A commonly applied scale in phosphorus management is a sociopolitical scale, which often includes levels such as the global, the EU, the national and the local (Chowdhury *et al.*, 2014; Rosemarin and Ekane, 2016). Another is a hydrological scale that might include river-basin, sub-catchment, hillslope and plot-levels (Hewett *et al.*, 2009; Reaney *et al.*, 2019). In all cases, the choice of applied scale and level of focus means deciding which dimensions and dynamics to analyse and which to exclude, which is a necessary process to a certain extent (Gibson, Ostrom and Ahn, 2000). However, when analysing multi-faceted, complex systems it is important to recognise that the delineation of a scale, or levels within a scale for the purpose of analysis neither implies that these are the only possible scales and levels that could be important, nor that they are isolated from each other (Cash *et al.*, 2006; Buizer, Arts and Kok, 2011; Vervoort *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, when developing phosphorus management strategies, it is necessary to consider interactions across and between the applied scales that contribute to the behaviour of the system overall (Hewett *et al.*, 2009; Moss and Newig, 2010; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2014; Hüesker and Moss, 2015; Rosemarin and Ekane, 2016). For example, cross-level interactions mean dynamics at lower levels can contribute to those at higher scales, as we can see from critical source areas that contribute disproportionately to the eutrophication of a larger catchment in a hydrological scale (Pionke, Gburek and Sharpley, 2000; Doody *et al.*, 2012). Equally, cross-scalar interactions mean that disruptions to global trade in mined phosphate (typically observed at a global sociopolitical level) can contribute to lower phosphorus losses at the hydrological level of the field, by driving lower applications of mineral fertiliser by an individual farmer (Zou, Zhang and Davidson, 2022).

These interactions necessitate the development of management strategies that are aligned across both levels and scales to achieve sustainable phosphorus use (Hewett *et al.*, 2009; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2014; Rosemarin and Ekane, 2016; Reaney *et al.*, 2019). To support this process, this research explores the cross-level and cross-scalar interactions that emerged in a place-based transdisciplinary case study on eutrophication around a sub-catchment in Stockholm. Using the perspective of change-agents, (Cash *et al.*, 2006; Buizer, Arts and Kok, 2011; Vervoort *et al.*, 2012) this case study identifies frictions and synergies that occurred due to the interplay between different scales and levels for phosphorus management (Cash *et al.*, 2006). By doing so, we elucidate the implications that inter-level and inter-scalar interplay have for addressing the ‘wicked problem’ of phosphorus-driven eutrophication and the achievement of WFD goals.

2. Methodology

2.1 The Case

Stockholm is built across 14 islands where Lake Mälaren, an important source of drinking water, joins the Baltic Sea (Mälarens vattenvårdsförbund, no date). Its large catchment of 22,603 km² (Wallin *et al.*, 2000) means many drivers impact its water quality, including Stockholm municipality’s population of 1 million (Stockholms Stad, 2023). These pressures mean that 61% of Stockholm’s waterbodies fail to reach good nutrient status according to the obligations in the WFD (Directive 2000/60/EC Establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy, 2000) and the Northern Baltic River Basin Management Plan (Vatteninformationssystem Sverige, 2023). Consequently, Stockholm Municipality has developed both a city-wide action plan (Stockholms Stad, 2015; Vattenmyndigheten Norra Östersjön, 2016) and ‘local action plans’ for scaling down the WFD and bringing each of Stockholm’s designated waterbodies to ‘good’ status (Stockholms Stad, 2015).

The local action plans modelled phosphorus sources to the individual waterbodies and in this process identified certain land-uses and user groups as relevant for phosphorus management in the sub-catchment. In several local action plansⁱⁱⁱ, allotment gardens were modelled as potential sources. Although measuring urban agriculture’s potential contribution to water bodies’ phosphorus load not widely done and challenging, there is evidence that these spaces can be nutrient ‘hotspots’ in cities and thus may pose a risk under certain conditions (Wielemaker *et al.*, 2019; van de Vlasakker, Tonderski and Metson, 2022; Sieczko *et al.*, 2023). In response, representatives from Sweden’s and Stockholm’s Allotment Garden Association initiated a research project with the University of Linköping to better understand this issue, using Lake Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön as a case-study (**Box 1**). Initial interviews aimed to understand the perceived role of allotment gardens in the eutrophication of Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön at large. However, these interviews provided insights into the wider challenges of downscaling the Northern Baltic River Basin Management Plan to sub-catchment plans and carrying out concrete measures. The participants identified actors and drivers that were located at multiple different levels; therefore, the focus of the research shifted to explore these scalar aspects of phosphorus management through a consultative transdisciplinary lens (Djenontin and Meadow, 2018; Lam *et al.*, 2021).

Box 1: Phosphorus losses in Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön

The lake’s catchment is highly altered by the introduction of impervious surfaces and artificial drainage, and mostly consists of industrial, residential and commercial areas, roadways and carparks. Only one third is comprised of green areas, including forest and allotment gardens (Stockholms Stad *et al.*, 2021). The high proportion of impervious surfaces mean that phosphorus transport in stormwater (urban runoff) is a key concern. There are no direct discharges from wastewater treatment plants into the lake; however, combined sewage

ⁱⁱⁱ(Water Revival Systems, 2019; Stockholms Stad and Stockholm Vatten och Avfall, 2020; Stockholms Stad and Stockholm Vatten och Avfall, 2020; Stockholms Stad *et al.*, 2021; Stockholms Stad, Stockholm Vatten och Avfall and Tyresån, 2022)

overflows can affect Lake Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön during heavy rainfall (Stockholms Stad *et al.*, 2021; Stockholm Vatten och Avfall, 2021). Internal loading of legacy P into the water column from lake sediment is also a concern (Stockholms Stad *et al.*, 2021).

2.2 Participant engagement

A total of thirty-eight participants were engaged, through interviews and/or workshop participation (**Table 1**). Participants were selected according to their agency and role in phosphorus management (Lyon *et al.*, 2020), and efforts were made to engage actors across the multiple 'levels' identified during document and interview analysis. Interviewees were included based on their ability to influence phosphorus dynamics at any given level by directly, or indirectly impacting land-use and wastewater management, which are major drivers of eutrophication in the urban environment (Hobbie *et al.*, 2017; Yang and Toor, 2018). The local action plans for implementing the WFD were used to identify an initial list of relevant actors, which was expanded through reviewing academic literature, policy and strategy documents, online searches and snowballing (Heckathorn and Cameron, 2017). Time considerations and the exploratory nature of the case-study meant that 'depth' rather than 'breadth' was pursued; however, an important limitation is that it was not possible to recruit participants from some key institutions including Stockholm's Development and Planning Boards.

Table 1: Institutional and individual stakeholders engaged in the research project, across sociopolitical levels.

Level	Sector	Organisation	Scope
National	Government agency	Swedish Environmental Protection Agency ^a (Naturvårdsverket)	Proposal and implementation of environmental policy.
	Trade organisation	Swedish Water ^a (Svenskt Vatten)	Trade organisation for water and wastewater operators that conducts advocacy work at national and EU-level.
	NGO	Swedish Allotment Garden Association ^{ab} (Koloniträdgårdsförbundet)	National organisation of allotment garden associations
	Private company	RagnSells ^a	Waste management, recycling and environmental services.
River-basin	NGO	The Mälaren Water Conservation Association (Mälarens vattenvårdsförbund ^a)	An NGO that carries out monitoring, attempts to drive collaboration around water quality and provide information. Members include governmental and non-governmental organisations.
County	Regional-level state authority	Stockholm County Administrative Board ^b (Länsstyrelsen Stockholm)	Implementation of national goals at county level. Allocates grants, issues permits for activities that may have impacts on aquatic environments.
City	Multi-municipality association	North Water ^a (Norrsvatten)	Produces drinking water (primarily from lake Mälaren) for an association of 14 municipalities.
	Municipal government (decision-making)	City Executive Board ^{ab} (Kommunstyrelsen)	Implements the political decisions of the city council.
	Municipal government (implementation)	Stockholm Traffic Board ^{ab} (Trafikkontoret)	Roadway and park management, and role in stormwater handling.
	Municipal government (implementation)	Stockholm Environmental Board ^a (Miljöförvaltningen)	Environmental supervision and monitoring. Responsible for developing and coordinating local action plans (WFD).
	Municipal company	Stockholm Water and Waste ^{ab} (Stockholm Vatten och Avfall)	Municipal company for wastewater treatment, drinking water production and waste handling
	NGO	Stockholms Allotment Association ^{ab} (Stockholms Koloniträdgårdar)	Association of allotment gardens in Stockholm.
Sub-catchment	District government	Bromma District Council ^b (Bromma stadsdelsförvaltning)	Responsible the management of parks and other aspects of the urban environment.
Micro	NGO	Individual allotment associations ^{ab} (Koloniträdgårdsförening)	Organisations that rent land for allotments (primarily from Stockholm municipality).
Micro	Individual	Allotment gardeners ^{ab}	Individual allotment gardeners
<i>Nature of involvement in the research: a) interview, b) workshop</i>			

2.3 Data collection and analysis

Data collection occurred between May 2022 and February 2023. Document analysis, interviews and workshops were used to identify, from the perspective of stakeholders, 1) the scales and levels that were important for phosphorus management, 2) the driving factors of phosphorus dynamics and how they were located across those scales, and 3) the implications the cross-scalar and cross level interactions for phosphorus management in this context. Interviews and document analysis were used to explore current perceptions of these interactions, while the workshops enabled researchers to observe how these interactions emerged in-situ during action-focussed discussions of a specific case for phosphorus management (the allotment gardens).

Documentary sources included legislation, policy statements, and strategies focussing on WFD implementation, water quality and environmental issues, wastewater treatment, stormwater management and land-use planning. Key documents were the Northern Baltic Sea River Basin Management Plan (Vattenmyndigheten Norra Östersjön, 2016), Stockholm Municipality's city-wide action plan to achieve good water status (Stockholms Stad, 2015), and the local action plan for achieving good water status for Lake Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön (Stockholms Stad *et al.*, 2021)

The interview guideline was informed by the framework developed by Metson *et al.*, (2015), that emphasised the necessity to identify *drivers* (factors that directly or indirectly impact phosphorus dynamics) across multiple social, technical and ecological categories (**Figure 1**) and across spatial and temporal scales. In accordance with this framework, interview questions attempted to systematically identify diverse drivers. Seventeen institutional actors participated in in-depth, semi-structured interviews in English. Topics included major sources and drivers of phosphorus pollution in Stockholm's lakes, current strategies for addressing the issue, and management challenges (interview guideline in **Appendix 1.**) Interviews lasted approximately one hour and were conducted online or in person. They were also used to identify further participants for the workshops, and to develop workshop activities.

Two half-day workshops were conducted in Swedish, involving twenty-three participants. Participants were asked to consider the role that the micro-level could play in achieving WFD goals in Stockholm, using the example of the allotment gardens. The researchers presented soil samples and nutrient budgets from the allotment sites, which showed high soil P and excess P applications (**Appendix 2**), as boundary objects to illustrate the potential opportunity for more sustainable nutrient management in the allotments. This discussion entry point enabled the exploration of multi-scalar and multi-level dynamics that emerged in-situ when actors across sociopolitical levels discussed a novel level for strategy development. The first workshop engaged governmental actors and representatives from Stockholm and Sweden's allotment associations. The second workshop involved representatives from Stockholm's allotment association, and those from individual allotment sites. The participants were divided into small groups with one mediator / notetaker, and a Dictaphone to record discussions. In both workshops, participants were first asked to produce and present individual 'mental models' (Jones *et al.*, 2011; Lynam and Brown, 2012), in small groups, that pictorially represented their understanding of the relationships between allotments, water quality and urban sustainability overall. The mental models were constructed from 'factors' (E.g. food production, information) that mediated these relationships. The factors were derived from interviews; however, participants could add their own (**Appendix 3**). The most selected factors were used as a basis for small group discussions, where participants first suggested actions that they, or their organisation, could take to mitigate eutrophication directly or indirectly by acting on those factors. They were then asked to suggest actions that other organisations could take. Finally, the actions were presented to all participants, who were then asked to vote for the actions they thought would be most valuable for improving nutrient use and mitigating any losses (workshop outline in **Appendix 4.**)

2.4 Data Analysis

Interview, workshop and documentary data were analysed in an iterative process using a qualitative content analysis approach, which combined deductive and inductive approaches to coding the data (Cho and Lee, 2014). Initial coding of the data was deductive, using codes derived from the framework developed by Metson *et al.*

al., (2015). This maximised the identification of a broad range of system drivers. Successive rounds used codes derived inductively from the data that categorised text according to the scale and/or level they were located at by participants (e.g. 'national' & 'micro'), what kind of interaction was occurring (e.g. 'inter-sociopolitical level'), and the nature of the drivers that were participating in the interactions (e.g. 'legislation' or 'goal alignment.'). The final stage was identifying which interactions acted as barriers or enablers in the case study context, to draw conclusions about the implications that cross-scalar and cross-level interactions have for phosphorus management (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Social, ecological and technological drivers of the phosphorus challenge. Adapted from Metson et al., (2015).

Phase 1: Determine scales, levels and drivers

Phase 2: Identify cross-level and cross scalar interactions

Phase 3: Establish barriers and enablers

Figure 2: Process of cross-level and cross-scalar analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 The scales and levels for phosphorus management

Two interacting scales emerged as important for phosphorus management: a sociopolitical scale and a spatially nested hydrological scale (Table 2). The sociopolitical scale contains the EU, national, river-basin (referred to as the river-basin authority), county, and city levels (Figure 3), all of which were described as important for mitigating phosphorus-driven eutrophication in the case-study context. This finding aligns with previous research on Swedish water governance that identified a polycentric governance structure (Moss and Newig, 2010; Jager *et al.*, 2016; Söderberg, 2016; Nykvist, Borgström and Boyd, 2017). Levels differed according to the hydrological level(s) they were concerned with, and their power over political goal setting, decision-making and resources at other levels. However, they were not homogeneous and contained multiple organisations with overlapping jurisdictions (Jager *et al.*, 2016; Nykvist, Borgström and Boyd, 2017). The hydrological scale consisted of the river-basin, city (referred to as the sewershed^{iv}), sub-catchment and micro-levels, where the hydrology at a given level was a product of biogeophysical, social and infrastructural elements (Figure 3). The addition of sewershed and micro-levels expands on the hydrological levels that have been highlighted as important for cross-scalar interactions in previous research on the implementation of the WFD (Hüesker and Moss, 2015).

Table 2: A summary of the levels within the interacting sociopolitical and hydrological scales and the drivers that indirectly

Socio-political Scale		Hydrological Scale	
Sociopolitical level	Key drivers	Hydrological level	Drivers of P dynamics
EU	EU legislation		
National	National legislation and legislative power		
River-basin authority	Funding.	River-basin	
County	Development of legally binding river-	Sewershed	Agriculture. ^a
River basin autonomy	Development of legally binding river-	Sub-catchment	Urban land use. ^a
City	Development of legally binding river-	Micro	Small drains. ^a
			WWTPs. ^a
			Horse farms. ^a
			Internal loading. ^a
			Natural background load. ^a
			Rainfall

Figure 3: Scales and levels for phosphorus management in Stockholm. Hydrological levels are aligned with the sociopolitical level that has direct responsibility for strategy development for WFD implementation at this level.

	Mediation of access to state funding.		
City	Strategy development for WFD	Sewershed	Capacity and degree of wastewater treatment
<i>Municipal political decision-making bodies</i>	Implementation at city and sub-catchment level.	<i>The extent covered by Stockholm's centralised wastewater treatment system.</i>	Percentage of combined pipelines
<i>Municipal boards and companies</i>	Land-use planning power within municipal boundaries.		Percentage of impervious surfaces
<i>Local action plan working groups</i>	Wastewater infrastructure planning, implementation and management.		Misconnections and combined sewage overflows (CSOs)
<i>District administrations</i>	Policy-making.		Pipe leakage
	Policy implementation.		Rainfall
	Funding from municipal taxation.		

^{iv} The term 'sewershed' refers to the water catchment created by sewer and stormwater networks that direct water to Stockholm's WWTPs to be emitted as point sources into coastal waters (Ventura and Kim, 1993). The municipality currently has 2 WWTPs (Broma and Henriksdal); however, Broma is being decommissioned and its influent will be redirected to Henriksdal (Stockholm Vatten och Avfall [Stockholm Water and Waste], no date).

	Sub-catchment <i>Drainage area produced by natural catchment and technical catchment.</i>	Land-use type and area ^b Topography Stormwater treatment facilities ^b Internal loading ^c Contribution from upstream waterbodies ^d Misconnections and CSOs (links to city-wide WWT system) Rainfall
	Micro <i>Smallest spatial scale differentiated in hydrological modelling and phosphorus management strategies</i>	Land-use (loss co-efficient is applied according to land-use types) ^e Stormwater infrastructure Rainfall
a)	Derived from North Baltic Sea River Basin Management Plan	
b)	Requirements of the StormTac model that was used to calculate stormwater (diffuse) loading from land-based sources.	
c)	Derived from ALcontrol assessment (ALcontrol Laboratories and SLU, 2019; Stockholms Stad <i>et al.</i> , 2021).	
d)	Bällstaån stream is considered a major contributor and has its own action plan (Stockholms Stad <i>et al.</i> , 2021).	
e)	Derived from StormTac database.	

3.2 Cross sociopolitical level interactions, and implications

Eight key drivers (factors that directly or indirectly shape phosphorus dynamics) were seen to interact across sociopolitical levels to inhibit or enable phosphorus management: goals, institutional norms, legislation, the interpretation and enforcement of legislation, the availability of funding, collaboration and knowledge exchange, and the implementation of infrastructure (Table 3).

Table 3: Cross sociopolitical level interactions that emerge as the result of the distribution and state of drivers across levels, and their implications for phosphorus management in this context.			
Sociopolitical level	Driver	State of Driver	Overall implication for phosphorus management
EU	Legislation: WFD ^a	WFD mandates improvements in water quality and P management at river basin and sub-catchment level.	Phosphorus management and water quality goals are not sufficiently embedded across the relevant sociopolitical levels. Changing this is essential for implementing phosphorus management in a high-density city, where there is limited space and competing values around how the space should be used. This includes a high number of policy goals that must be implemented at city-level.
	Goals: multiple priorities	Multiple goals originate from this level, including wastewater system decarbonisation.	
National	Legislation: Swedish Environmental Code ^b	The WFD as it is transposed in the Swedish Environmental code and Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) prohibits the deterioration of water quality.	
	Institutional norms: Prioritisation of water quality	Improving water quality is a policy goal and legal requirement; however, the political mandate from this level is considered weak.	
	Goals: multiple priorities	Multiple goals originate from this level, including increasing housing.	

River-basin authority	Legal powers: RBMPs	Improving water quality is embedded in legally binding RBMPs	
County	Legal powers: jurisdiction over land-use planning	Have jurisdiction over land-use decisions that have a high likelihood of negatively impacting water quality.	
	Interpretation of legislation: Interpretation of WFD / EQS	WFD / EQS are interpreted strictly by county administrative boards.	
City	Policy: city and local action plans for improving water quality	Improving water quality is a policy goal and embedded in city and local action plans for achieving better water quality.	
	Institutional norms: prioritisation of water quality, planning	Water quality has not been fully embedded into the institutional norms of all the municipal boards. This means missed opportunities to implement water quality infrastructures alongside other projects, and frequent planning clashes with other goals.	
National	Legislation: division of responsibility at city-level	Legislation contains unclear divisions of responsibility for water quality management at city level.	Strict interpretation of the WFD / EQS at county-level favours the implementation of phosphorus management. However, this is inhibited by a lack of legislation that defines responsibility for managing urban run-off at city-level, and insufficient legal powers at city level. The need to negotiate responsibilities at city-level is slowing implementation.
County	Interpretation of legislation: interpretation of WFD / EQS	WFD / EQS are interpreted strictly by county administrative boards, which can achieve prioritisation of water quality goals.	
City	Legal powers: local action plans	Local action plans are not legally binding, so other drivers are important for implementation.	
	Division of responsibility: responsibility for stormwater infrastructure	Division of responsibility for managing urban run-off is not defined at national level. Therefore, it needs to be negotiated at city-level, which is an ongoing process.	
National	Legislation: Public Water Services Act ^c	The fees charged by municipal water and waste companies may not exceed the amount needed to cover the necessary costs of building and running wastewater treatment and drinking water production facilities.	The funding and capacity for implementing phosphorus management at city-level are misaligned with responsibility for implementing the WFD at this level. Stockholm Water and Waste are the body legally responsible for managing stormwater infrastructures. However, current funding streams are deemed inadequate for the company to implement the mandated infrastructure. Instead, they rely on the construction of infrastructure by other municipal boards. This slows implementation of phosphorus management.
	Funding: national funds for water projects	National-level funding is accessible to municipal boards, but not to municipal companies.	
City	Division of responsibility: responsibility for stormwater infrastructure	The municipal company, Stockholm Water and Waste has been designated legal ownership and responsibility for stormwater infrastructure.	
	Interpretation of legislation: interpretation of Public Water Services Act	The municipal council interprets the Public Water Services Act to decide the fees that Stockholm Water and Waste can charge.	
	Funding: funding for Stockholm Water and Waste	National funding for water quality projects is not available to Stockholm Water and Waste.	

		Wastewater treatment fees are inadequate for Stockholm Water and Waste to invest significantly in stormwater infrastructure.	
	Stormwater infrastructure: Implementation of stormwater infrastructure	Stormwater infrastructure must be built by other municipal boards and their ownership transferred to Stockholm Water and Waste.	
EU	Goals: multiple priorities	Multiple goals originate from this level, including the WFD and climate change mitigation.	High urban density and a high number of priorities that must be implemented at city level are driving a shift towards green spaces and infrastructures for nutrient management. This is because they are seen to offer 'multi-functionality,' whereby multiple priorities can be addressed simultaneously. However, the capacity to design and implement these kinds of measures is seen as low, due to limited funds, time and support. All of which inhibit the embedding of 'multi-functional thinking' into institutional norms at city-level.
National	Goals: multiple priorities Support: support for capacity development	Multiple goals originate from this level, including climate change adaptation. Limited political mandate and provision of support for embedding 'multi-functional thinking' into norms across the city-level.	
City	Goals: multiple priorities Institutional norm: multi-functional infrastructure Institutional norm: multi-functional thinking	Multiple goals must be implemented at this level, including water quality improvements, housing development, climate change adaptation and mitigation, and increasing biodiversity. Interest in green spaces and infrastructures is growing. There is a perceived need for city-level actors to think in 'multi-functional' ways to integrate multiple priorities.	
a) Directive 2000/60/EC Establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy, 2000 b) SFS 1998:808 Miljöbalk [Swedish Environmental Code], 1998 c) SFS 2006:412 Lag Om Allmänna Vattentjänster [Act on Public Water Services], 2006			

3.2.1 Phosphorus management requires greater goal alignment across sociopolitical levels

Interviews indicated that WFD goals are not sufficiently embedded into institutional norms across sociopolitical levels to achieve phosphorus management implementation in a context where multiple priorities and jurisdictions co-exist. At city-level, several municipal boards have a role in implementing local action plans because they have jurisdiction over key water quality drivers including land-use and wastewater infrastructure. However, as in other research (Moss, 2004; Cettner *et al.*, 2013; Söderberg, 2016; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020; Rowbottom *et al.*, 2022), interviewees perceived a persistent 'siloeing' of thinking and priorities that reflected a failure to integrate water quality goals into norms at this level. As explained by one interviewee:

"If they are remodelling a street that can be a perfect time to ... have some kind of measure that will clean the water, instead of these action [plans] coming and saying I'll put it here. Because it's cheaper if you already are there and changing things ... and that we miss when we can't inform everybody on how to work with water." (Interviewee 7)

Aligning with other construction projects was seen as an important enabler of implementation of water quality measures, as has been argued elsewhere (Tscheikner-Gratl *et al.*, 2016). As referenced in the previous quote, this is key where multiple municipal boards have jurisdiction over relevant infrastructures but don't have the necessary expertise in water quality issues. Currently, the municipal boards are not proactively communicating opportunities and aligning their plans, resulting in missed opportunities to implement water quality measures alongside other developments. This indicates that water quality goals are not fully integrated into planning norms. As found previously (Cettner *et al.*, 2013; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020; Rowbottom *et al.*, 2022), this poses an important barrier to the implementation of phosphorus management and the WFD.

The picture is further complicated by the responsibility that city-level actors have for implementing a variety of other existing and emerging goals. Goals that originate from multiple sociopolitical levels, including “the legislation and the EU directives that we have to look at and at the same time we have the goals from the political part, and in the city.” (Interviewee 16) A significant challenge in a high-density city. Water quality goals must be successfully prioritised and, where possible, integrated with these goals at city-level to facilitate the mitigation of phosphorus losses (Söderberg, 2016; Stafford-Smith *et al.*, 2017; Nieuwenhuis *et al.*, 2021). Actors identified a variety of goals that have implications for phosphorus management, including: urban development and increasing housing in the city, maintaining the direct re-use of sewage sludge on agricultural land, improving urban biodiversity, and adapting to and mitigating climate change. Development was most commonly stated as competing with water quality goals. Clashes frequently arose between the municipal boards over plans for particular micro-level sites, slowing the implementation of WFD goals, as found in other studies (Söderberg, 2016; Sandström, Söderberg and Nilsson, 2020). There was a sense that water quality was prioritised over development more than in the past, with one interviewee stating that in the event of a clash they “*probably would get a pond instead of the building.*” (Interviewee 7) They attributed this to a strong embedding of water quality goals at county level, and their refusal of permits for projects that could negatively impact water quality according to WFD rules.

Nevertheless, achieving the prioritisation of water quality goals was seen as an ongoing challenge during efforts to plan and implement water quality measures. One interviewee stated that it was considered inappropriate to block other plans for spaces:

“Every time there is a new plan for housing or something they contact us and say, ‘We’re planning a new kindergarten and houses here, and we see that you have a space for a dam, oh what should we do?’ And that’s very good, but then we haven’t come that far maybe on that particular place and maybe there are some obstacles ... so we can’t say ‘Oh stop it,’ or ‘You have to clear that space.’” (Interviewee 6)

This illustrates that, at city-level, the WFD is not being translated into appropriate strategic decisions on land-use (Söderberg, 2016; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020). Instead, ongoing clashes between policy goals and jurisdictions in urban water management inhibit WFD implementation (Barbosa, Fernandes and David, 2012; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020; Sandström *et al.*, 2020). The failure to implement planned water quality measures has serious implications for whether WFD goals can be achieved in Stockholm because, as stated by one interviewee, it is projected that all the phosphorus management measures outlined in the local action plans need be implemented to achieve WFD targets:

“If the total load that has to be removed is 80 kilos maybe, we have tried to get measures that take away 120, a little bit more, but in many action plans it has not been possible. So, when the action plans come to us, we should have to do everything in order to reach good chemical and ecological status.” (Interviewee 6)

There are a limited number of appropriate sites at the micro-level, which means there may not be alternatives if they are used for other purposes. Together, these issues suggest that the embedding of water quality goals into planning norms is incompatible with the challenges of WFD implementation in the urban environment. Fundamentally, it may not be possible to achieve WFD goals in high-density cities if the challenges posed by high and increasing infrastructure density are not recognised and addressed (Kaur, Hewage and Sadiq, 2022).

In light of these issues, participants saw a need for a stronger political mandate at both city and national-level to drive a greater embedding of water quality goals into the institutional norms of the municipal boards at city-level. Several interviewees also identified a need for better guidance and processes to facilitate the prioritisation of water quality goals. This reflects other research findings (Ferguson *et al.*, 2013; Söderberg, 2016; Glaas, Hjerpe and Jonsson, 2018; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020).

3.2.2 Legislation disfavours the prioritisation of phosphorus management at city-level

Legislative drivers potentially have an essential role to play here, as several participants saw legislation as important for facilitating goal alignment across sociopolitical levels. The WFD, the Swedish Environmental Code

and water quality standards for water, and the legally binding River Basin Management Plans were seen as essential for achieving the prioritisation of water quality goals at city level, as has been found previously (Dawson *et al.*, 2018). However, the power at city-level for enforcing the WFD was seen as weak in comparison to the national and river-basin authority levels, despite its high level of responsibility for WFD implementation (Söderberg, 2016; Glaas, Hjerpe and Jonsson, 2018). The local action plans for implementing the WFD in individual sub-catchments are not legally binding, so other drivers were important for their implementation. A key driver was the interpretation and enforcement of the WFD by the County Administrative Boards (Länsstyrelsen). In the event of clashes between water quality and other city-level priorities, the strict interpretation of the WFD by the County Administrative Board was seen as an essential driver for the prioritisation of water quality goals. As stated by one interviewee:

“Our gold card is that we have the EU legislation and we also have our Länsstyrelsen [the County Administrative Board]. ... And the good thing for us is that our county board has been quite hard on our Stadsbyggnadskontoret [City Planning Board] and Exploateringskontoret [City Development Board] to really look into the water issues.” (Interviewee 7)

In this case, legislative drivers at national and EU levels, and their interpretation and enforcement at county-level, can enable the prioritisation of water quality and phosphorus management where city-level legal powers don't exist. However, as discussed previously, this is not currently translating into the strong prioritisation and implementation of WFD goals at city level. Further challenges are posed by national-level legislation that were thought to poorly define responsibility for managing urban run-off, which meant it had to be interpreted, negotiated and decided at city-level. As summarised by one interviewee:

“It's many different legislations that do not really talk to each other and that says different things. So according to which one you're reading, you get one idea, but then on the other hand, there's another legislation saying something else.” (Interviewee 16)

Stockholm Water and Waste have been attributed responsibility for the city's stormwater infrastructure through political decisions made at city-level. However, the transfer of the ownership of infrastructure is still ongoing and continues to hinder implementation efforts at this level. Poorly defined responsibilities and ownership over stormwater infrastructure have persisted as barriers since they were first identified by Cettner *et al.*, in 2013 (see also Glaas, Hjerpe and Jonsson, 2018; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020). Again, this suggests a need for better systems and processes for the prioritisation of water quality goals (Söderberg, 2016) and several interviewees saw a need for change in legislation to support efforts at the city-level.

3.2.3 Misalignments between responsibilities and funding reduce capacity for implementation

Legislative drivers also played a central role in defining capacity of city-level actors to implement phosphorus management by defining the funding available to city-level actors (Cettner *et al.*, 2014; Söderberg, 2016; Qiao *et al.*, 2019; Wihlborg, Sörensen and Alkan Olsson, 2019; Suleiman, 2021). Stockholm municipality's strong tax base and power to determine how tax funds are used were seen as significant enablers of implementation. However, participants identified important misalignments between legislation, funding and the level of responsibility for implementing the WFD at city-level.

A key friction identified by participants was created by misalignments between the responsibilities attributed to the municipality's water company, Stockholm Water and Waste and the legislation and decision making that defined its funding streams. The company is responsible for a significant number of wastewater measures in the local action plans, including reducing misconnections and leakages in the sewer system, separating parts of the sewer network that are combined, and implementing infrastructure for treating urban run-off (Stockholms Stad *et al.*, 2021). Unlike the municipal boards, municipal wastewater companies like Stockholm Water and Waste are unable to access other forms of national-level funding for water quality projects. Instead, their funding streams are defined by The Act on Public Water Services (Lag om allmänna vattentjänster [Act on Public Water Services], 2006), which states that the fee that municipal water companies charge customers for providing clean water and

sewerage services may not exceed the amount needed to cover the costs of building and maintaining the facility (SFS 2006:412 Lag om allmänna vattentjänster [Act on Public Water Services], 2006). The Act is interpreted by political decision-making bodies at city-level, which ultimately decide the fees that it can charge for its services. There was a perception that, together, these drivers resulted in inadequate funding for Stockholm Water and Waste to directly finance the expected water quality infrastructure. According to interviewees, this means that Stockholm Water and Waste primarily relies on municipal boards like the Traffic Board (Trafikkontoret) financing stormwater facilities and then transferring them ownership. Overall, this was seen as driving a low rate of investment in new infrastructure by the company and inhibiting the implementation of phosphorus management at city-level:

“The water company tries to do it as much as possible, but ... they only build new things when something breaks. So, if a pipe in the street breaks, they go in there and they try to replace it, maybe a little bit more, and this is like the investment level that they are working at, at the moment.” (Interviewee 7)

Addressing these misalignments was seen as important for implementing the WFD at sewershed and sub-catchment level in a reasonable timeframe, while still enabling the implementation of the company’s other priorities.

3.2.4 Goal integration is driving a cultural shift towards ‘multi-functional’ spaces and infrastructures

Ensuring the implementation of water quality goals was a continuous challenge in the urban environment of Stockholm, where multiple priorities existed that had to be implemented in limited available space. Many participants saw this as driving a cultural shift towards measures and spaces that are considered multi-functional, as a way of circumventing conflict over micro-level spaces by integrating multiple goals.

Creating synergies between goals was seen as a key enabler of phosphorus management, and an essential challenge, with one participant asking, *“together with those who work with climate adaptation and such, how do we get the message that climate adaptation and water quality are very often connected if we do it in a good way?”* (Interviewee 3) For several interviewees, the answer was using green spaces and infrastructures like rain beds or green roofs for nutrient capture and delivering other benefits. This reflects ongoing practitioner and academic discourses that promote blue-green infrastructures as a means to integrate and deliver multiple benefits in urban spaces (Kiparsky *et al.*, 2013; Kuitert, Willems and Volker, 2023). However, managing infrastructures and green spaces for multiple benefits is not the norm (Cettner, Söderholm and Viklander, 2012). For example, workshop participants highlighted a lack of strategies at any sociopolitical level for integrating nutrient concerns, current land-use values and the potential benefits that could be delivered by the allotment gardens. This is despite the modelled role of allotments in phosphorus losses, and the fact that actors across sociopolitical levels recognised many potential urban sustainability benefits of allotments. Benefits that included mitigating the urban heat island effect, increasing urban biodiversity, maintaining knowledge of food production and improving health and wellbeing (Speak, Mizgajski and Borysiak, 2015; Borysiak, Mizgajski and Speak, 2017; Cabral *et al.*, 2017).

Consequently, several participants saw a need for greater ‘multi-functional’ thinking across norms at the city-level. In the words of one participant:

“Taking care of the blue green spaces along the roads... did not use to be the part of the job. But guess what? Now it is, that's the point. So, we need to make sure that people ... take responsibility as a whole, as a team, right? Otherwise, you have the silo kind of mentality that, ‘oh, I'm not looking at roads, I'm not looking at pipes and such.” (Interviewee 12)

Embedding multi-functional thinking into city-level norms was seen as an important means to achieve the implementation of measures for managing phosphorus. According to several participants, this will require organisations to develop new knowledge and to work more collaboratively with actors across sociopolitical levels. This process was seen to require a stronger political mandate from city and national-level political actors, which translated into the provision of money, time and the support needed to work in new ways. These are frequently

suggested as enabling factors in sustainable urban water management (Cettner *et al.*, 2013; Wihlborg, Sörensen and Alkan Olsson, 2019; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020; Suleiman, 2021).

3.3 Cross-scalar interactions, and implications

Our analysis has demonstrated that cross-sociopolitical level interactions have important implications for phosphorus management by facilitating, inhibiting and shaping the actions of actors across the sociopolitical scale. This illustrates that there is no single sociopolitical level that is important for addressing eutrophication, despite the formulation of specific sociopolitical levels for governance around hydrological levels. The importance of multiple sociopolitical levels for shaping outcomes for phosphorus management is further demonstrated by the cross-scalar interactions that are presented in this section. Drivers located across various sociopolitical levels could impact drivers across the hydrological scale by shaping and constraining actions. Likewise, hydrological drivers at different levels could influence sociopolitical drivers, by affecting decision-making across the sociopolitical scale and determining the feasibility and efficacy of management strategies. Knowledge of hydrological drivers and dynamics at different levels was an essential mediator of these cross-scalar interactions.

The key drivers that participated in cross-scalar interactions included the following hydrological drivers: infrastructure density, centralisation of stormwater treatment, level and capacity of treatment in wastewater treatment plants, and knowledge gaps and uncertainties regarding catchment and micro-level hydrological drivers and dynamics. These interacted with the following sociopolitical drivers: goals, institutional knowledge norms, legislation, legal power and funding (**Table 4**).

Table 4: Cross-scalar interactions that emerge as the result of the distribution and state of drivers across both sociopolitical and hydrological scales, and their implications for phosphorus management in this context.			
Scalar Level	Driver	State of Driver	Implication for phosphorus management
EU	Legislation: UWWTD ^a emerging legislation	Emerging legal requirement to reduce CSOs to < 1% dry weather flow.	Policy goals, legislation and high infrastructure density at sewershed and sub-catchment level interact to shape and severely constrain options for phosphorus management. Separating combined networks to address CSOs is an emerging goal. However, high infrastructure density at sub-catchment level means it may not be possible to introduce the decentralised stormwater treatment needed to deal with stormwater that is currently treated centrally. Therefore, drivers and dynamics at multiple hydrological levels need to be considered when planning the implementation of measures to achieve CSO reductions.
National	Goal: Decarbonisation	Decarbonisation goals limit the extent to which the built environment and can be changed.	
City	Goal: Reduction of CSOs	The reduction CSOs is an emerging goal to improve water quality and to support the application of sewage sludge to land.	
Sewershed	Infrastructure: Wastewater network	A high proportion of Stockholm’s wastewater network is combined, and a significant amount of stormwater is currently treated centrally in WWTP.	
	Water contaminants: Wastewater influent quality	Stormwater in influent reduces nutrient concentrations and introduces contaminants. This challenges certification through the REVAQ ^b sewage sludge quality scheme and therefore, its application to agricultural land.	
Sub-catchment	P sources: combined sewage overflows (CSOs)	Sub-catchments are impacted by P inputs from CSOs.	
	P sources: urban run-off (stormwater)	Urban run-off or stormwater is a major source of P in sub-catchments.	
	Infrastructure: infrastructure density	High infrastructure density means there is limited space for implementing decentralised stormwater management.	

Micro	Biophysical conditions: site characteristics	Not all available sites are appropriate for stormwater infrastructure. For example, if the land was reclaimed from lake-bed.	
National	Legislation: the Planning and Building Act ^c	The planning and building act obliges new building developments to treat their own stormwater onsite. However, the municipality has no legal powers to define what form of stormwater management should be implemented.	Existing legislation and rules (including the Planning and Building Act ^d and the Water Services Act ^e) give inadequate power to shape land-use and water planning according to sub-catchment level hydrological dynamics. This poses significant challenges to phosphorus management in-line with the intentions of the local action plans. Similar issues are apparent at micro-level and are seen to inhibit the development of strategies for allotment garden sites.
	Legislation: Public Water Services Act ^d	There are no obligations for existing building developments to treat stormwater. The Public Water Services Act obliges the municipal water company to provide sewage and stormwater treatment to existing developments. This is seen to favour end-of-pipe solutions.	
City	Legal powers: stormwater planning	The municipality has limited legal powers define what forms of stormwater infrastructure are placed and where.	
	Regulation: land-use guidelines	The municipality does not set requirements for nutrient management in allotment sites.	
Sub-catchment	Technical and natural hydrology: placement of stormwater treatment facilities	Topography and existing infrastructure, including pipe networks, define hydrological connectivity and where stormwater treatment facilities may be usefully placed.	
Micro	Biophysical conditions: site characteristics Land-use: nutrient management	Not all available sites are appropriate for stormwater infrastructure No existing guidelines on how nutrients should be managed in allotment sites	
National	Knowledge norms: legally binding action plans	Knowledge norms require low uncertainty in phosphorus sources, flows and drivers to make local action plans legally-binding.	Uncertainties and knowledge gaps around phosphorus dynamics at multiple levels are incompatible with knowledge standards at multiple sociopolitical levels. Uncertainties in knowledge of sub-catchment level dynamics prevents local action plans being made legally binding. Knowledge gaps also inhibit the use of green spaces and infrastructures for nutrient management. Participants identified several knowledge production norms as inhibiting knowledge production to address some of these uncertainties. Namely, limited collaboration across and between levels and scales, insufficient monitoring and evaluation, and lack of 'learning-by-doing' approaches.
City	Legal powers: Local action plans Knowledge production norms: cross-level collaboration	Local action plans for P management are not legally binding due to national knowledge norms and high uncertainty of sub-catchment level dynamics. Current levels of collaboration for knowledge across the city level, and across levels are insufficient. 'Learning-by-doing' approaches are uncommon. Insufficient monitoring and evaluation of measures.	
Sub-catchment	Knowledge certainty: sub-catchment P sources, flows and drivers	Knowledge of sub-catchment level P sources, flows and drivers has high uncertainty.	

Micro	<p>Knowledge gap: nutrient removal efficacy of green infrastructures</p> <p>Knowledge gap: Allotment P sources, flows, and drivers</p> <p>Knowledge production norms: cross-scalar collaboration</p>	<p>The efficacy of green infrastructures for nutrient removal is uncertain.</p> <p>Uncertainties in P sources, flows and drivers in allotment sites pose challenges to the development of management strategies.</p> <p>Current levels of collaboration across the city level, and across levels are minimal.</p>	
EU	<p>Legislation: WFD</p>	<p>The WFD was seen as an important driver for maintaining water quality goals at lower sociopolitical levels during sociopolitical changes like national or city level elections.</p>	<p>Participants highlighted the need to maintain water quality goals, expertise and measures over the ecological timeframes needed to observe system change. Funding and processes for knowledge exchange are essential to ensure the maintenance of water quality measures over the necessary timeframes and were seen as insufficient.</p>
National	<p>Government: government change</p> <p>Funding: funding for maintenance</p>	<p>Changes in government may lead to the deprioritisation of water quality goals and reductions in funding.</p> <p>Funding is unavailable for the long-term maintenance and monitoring of infrastructure..</p>	
City	<p>Government: government change</p> <p>Funding: funding for maintenance</p> <p>Knowledge: Knowledge of water quality management</p>	<p>Changes in government may lead to the deprioritisation of water quality goals and reductions in funding.</p> <p>Funding is unavailable for the long-term maintenance and monitoring of infrastructure.</p> <p>Knowledge of how to manage water quality and to maintain water quality measures like raingardens must be maintained across ecological timeframes.</p>	
Micro	<p>Knowledge: Knowledge of water quality management</p>	<p>Knowledge of good practices or how to maintain water quality measures must be maintained across ecological timeframes.</p>	
<p>a) The EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive is currently under revision (Directorate-General for Environment, 2022). b) The REVAQ certification scheme is operated by the Swedish Water & Wastewater Association, the Federation of Swedish Farmers (LRF), the Swedish Food Federation and the Swedish Food Retailers Federation (Swedish Water [Svensk Vatten], 2020). c) SFS 2010:900 Plan- och bygglag [The Planning and Building Act], 2010 d) SFS 2006:412 Lag Om Allmänna Vattentjänster [Act on Public Water Services], 2006</p>			

3.3.1 Hydrological drivers and other priorities constrain opportunities for phosphorus management

The cross-scalar interactions between water quality goals, other priorities and hydrological drivers shaped and often severely constrained opportunities for implementing phosphorus management. In our case study, participants identified two primary outcomes for phosphorus management that resulted from the cross-scalar interactions between these drivers. Firstly, hydrological drivers interacted with various goals to limit in absolute terms how much the built environment of the city could be changed to implement measures. Secondly, higher level goals could drive decision-making that is insensitive of phosphorus dynamics and hydrological drivers

at the sewershed, sub-catchment and micro-level. This could lead to undesirable outcomes such as increases in diffuse phosphorus losses at catchment level.

High infrastructure density, particularly coverage by impervious surfaces, was identified as an important driver of phosphorus dynamics at all hydrological levels and was expected to continuously increase due to urban development pressure. Interactions between high infrastructure density, higher level goals like climate change mitigation, and economic drivers placed strict limitations on the degree to which the built environment of the city could be transformed because *“It’s an extreme climate footprint to rebuild the cities, existing ones, so ... we say no to rebuilding existing cities. That will be an enormous climate impact, a lot of practical and juridical problems.”* (Interviewee 1) This limited the types of infrastructures that were considered for reducing diffuse urban phosphorus losses and constrained where they could be placed. Climate mitigation goals posed further challenges for managing phosphorus pollution as there was growing pressure to decarbonise the water sector. As expressed by one interviewee:

“In some years we should be resource neutral. Sometimes they call it climate neutral. And ... we who work a bit above that or below that we say that it’s going to be really difficult because in order to improve water quality we should do a lot of measures on the whole plant, like in the pipes and everything so that’s going to be difficult.” (Interviewee 6)

The goal of achieving neutrality in the wastewater sector existed at national and city-level, and was expected to be strengthened at EU-level in the revision of the Urban Water Waste Treatment Directive (UWWTD). However, it was unclear how the need to decarbonise the wastewater treatment sector at national-level would be resolved with the realities of significant infrastructural change to mitigate phosphorus losses at the sewershed level.

The pressure to implement climate mitigation goals demonstrates both the constraints that can be placed on phosphorus management at a hydrological level, and the need to consider hydrological drivers when implementing other goals. In other words, to consider wider systemic interactions and potential trade-offs (Metson *et al.*, 2015; McPhearson *et al.*, 2022; Metson, Brownlie and Spears, 2022). Similar dynamics could be observed when considering the move towards separating combined areas of Stockholm’s sewer system. The separation of stormwater from sewage in the wastewater system at the sewershed level was in line with two primary goals: improving the quality of sludge to support its re-use in agriculture and the reduction of combined sewage overflows (CSOs). At city level, despite some ongoing controversy at national level (Dagerskog and Olsson, 2020), the goal was to ensure that the sewage sludge produced in Stockholm can be applied to agricultural land. Separating the sewer system is seen as an enabler of sludge re-use because it redirects stormwater away from wastewater treatment plants that *“could contain metals and other pollutants, but not nutrients and organic matter, which the treatment plants are built for and which improve the sludge.”* (Interviewee 15) Redirecting stormwater was seen as important for improving the sludge quality and ensuring it can be certified for re-use in agriculture according to REVAQ requirements (a voluntary sludge quality certification scheme) which, in turn, would improve public acceptance of its use in agriculture.

A further driver of sewer separation is the EU’s UWWTD, which sets targets for the reduction of CSOs that are expected to be tightened in the upcoming revision of the directive. Reducing CSOs was seen as an essential goal because it can reduce the risks to health posed by the contamination of drinking water sources. There was also a perception at multiple sociopolitical levels that it can be a useful measure for reducing phosphorus inputs to waterbodies. This was reflected by its inclusion in city-level and local action plans for achieving WFD goals. However, how these higher-level goals are interpreted and implemented at sewershed level needs to be sensitive to drivers at sub-catchment level. As highlighted by several interviewees, separating combined systems does come with some potential drawbacks because in combined systems stormwater is carried to wastewater treatment plants. This can be *“good because you clean phosphorus and nitrogen in the treatment plants anyway, so it’s like this to double the functionality,”* (Interviewee 3) as put by one interviewee. Consequently, while separating the sewage and stormwater networks can reduce CSOs, it can also increase demand for decentralised stormwater treatment (Alves *et al.*, 2016). This creates some tensions, as outlined by one participant:

“If you have to avoid having more than 1% CSO you have to separate. But if, on the other hand, you're not allowed to have urban runoff untreated [in-line with the new UWWTD] then it will be very expensive.” (Interviewee 1)

In this quote, stringent requirements at the EU-level to both reduce CSOs and phosphorus losses through urban run-off could potentially conflict due to costs. However, further potential for conflict is perceptible when considering sub-catchment and micro level drivers. As aforementioned, in many sub-catchments it is deemed necessary to implement all the measures in the local action plans to achieve WFD goals, something which is already threatened by the competition for space. Furthermore, interviewees stated that it is unclear whether hydrological drivers at sub-catchment level like topography and the distribution of stormwater networks, as well as micro-level drivers like soil moisture, history of the site and land-use values will be favourable to the placement of new infrastructure. Therefore, it may be unrealistic to expect that the additional phosphorus load at sub-catchment level generated by separation of stormwater and sewage can be dealt with by implementing further decentralised facilities (Alves *et al.*, 2016). In this respect, the separation of the combined wastewater system according to phosphorus dynamics at the sewershed level may not be favourable to phosphorus management at the level of the sub-catchment. Consideration of sub-catchment level drivers may instead favour alternative measures or combinations of measures. This resonates with arguments that both centralised and decentralised solutions, as well as nature-based solutions, should be integrated for better management of both CSOs and urban run-off (Marsalek and Schreier, 2009; Cettner, Söderholm and Viklander, 2012; Alves *et al.*, 2016) For example, one interviewee suggested better upstream source control, while another highlighted that reductions in CSOs had already been achieved by increasing the capacity of the wastewater system.

These issues illustrate cross-scalar interactions can be extremely important where multiple priorities exist, and space is limited. Sub-catchment and micro-level hydrological drivers contribute to an extremely low degree of flexibility with regards to where water quality measures can be placed. This suggests that there needs to be a high level of awareness and prioritisation across sociopolitical levels to achieve WFD goals in this context.

3.3.2 Legislation inhibits planning decisions according to sub-catchment level phosphorus dynamics

Constraints generated by cross-scalar interactions between hydrological drivers and other priorities were seen as exacerbated by legislative drivers that prevented city-level actors implementing management strategies in-line with dynamics at sub-catchment level. Mirroring findings that inappropriate legislation can limit responsiveness to ecological drivers and inhibit the implementation of phosphorus management at city-level (Nykvist, Borgström and Boyd, 2017).

Participants cited legislation around stormwater as a key example. At present, the Planning and Building Act obliges new building developments to perform stormwater treatment on-site, with no obligations for existing buildings (SFS 2010:900 Plan- och bygglag [The Planning and Building Act], 2010). However, the municipality has no power to define what form of stormwater handling should be performed, as explained by one interviewee:

“You cannot say exactly what kind of stormwater handling you want in this place, you can only say this surface can be used for stormwater handling. ... You cannot say that you want tree planting here or something, that's not allowed.” (Interviewee 16)

This means that interpretation is left to the developer, which may pose challenges for the implementation of measures according to the phosphorus dynamics in a particular sub-catchment. Weaknesses in the Planning and Building Act (SFS 2010:900 Plan- och bygglag [The Planning and Building Act], 2010) have previously been identified as a barrier to sustainable urban water management in Sweden (Glaas, Hjerpe and Jonsson, 2018).

Similarly, while national and city-level guidance for the management of stormwater recommends that stormwater be managed close to its source, it is not supported by existing legislation. The Public Water Services Act (SFS 2006:412 Lag om allmänna vattentjänster [Act on Public Water Services], 2006) obliges municipal water companies to take responsibility for stormwater management, which can act as a driver that favours end-of-pipe rather than upstream management. The issue was summarised by an interviewee:

“Stockholm Water... have to take care of the stormwater, but maybe it would be better if the stormwater gets infiltrated outside the house, instead of put in a pipe, but the legislation says that they have to have a pipe. So, if someone says I want the pipe then they have to give them a pipe. So it's not always easy.” (Interviewee 7)

Participants in the second workshop also suggested that changing city-level regulation on land-use could be an enabler of better nutrient management at the micro-level of the allotments. They suggest changes in city-level rules and regulations that set expectations for how the allotment sites, leased from the city, should be managed. In the workshops it was suggested that introducing explicit guidelines for nutrient and water management in the allotment gardens could encourage actors at the micro-level to take greater responsibility for nutrient management, when combined with appropriate support. It was suggested that this could be added to existing environmental certification schemes that are provided by the Swedish Allotment Association and the municipality could support the process by providing incentives for certification like lower rates for land rental.

Overall, participants saw a need to address current unfavourable cross-scalar interactions largely attributed to unfavourable rules and legislation around land-use planning. Mitigating these interactions was important to facilitate changes in land-use and water management according to phosphorus dynamics at the sub-catchment and micro-level, as intended in the local action plans.

3.3.3 Uncertainties and knowledge gaps require changes in knowledge production norms

Legislation contributed to further unfavourable cross-scalar interactions, resulting from misalignments between city and national-level social norms that defined acceptable levels of uncertainty, and the knowledge of drivers and dynamics at relevant hydrological levels. As a wicked problem, eutrophication is characterised by high uncertainty and therefore, it is necessary to have strategies for operating under these conditions (Thornton *et al.*, 2013). However, uncertainties regarding phosphorus dynamics and drivers at sub-catchment level and knowledge gaps around the efficacy of green infrastructures for phosphorus management played a key role in whether certain strategies were considered viable, were funded or were given legal weight. This was seen as inhibiting the implementation of phosphorus management and as creating a need for changes in norms around knowledge production at city-level.

Uncertainties in available knowledge at sub-catchment level, were incompatible with the knowledge standards that were embedded in legislation at national level. This contributed to the lack of legal weight given to the local action plans:

“There are criteria in the legislation that you have for those action programmes, and you have to have good enough quality on the data ... And those things are not very good at the moment.” (Interviewee 16)

Uncertainty and knowledge gaps around hydrological drivers at various levels were also seen as playing a direct role in preventing the development of legislation around stormwater management. As explained by an interviewee:

“Normally the national authorities, when they are responsible for a law, they also take out little guidelines for how it's supposed to be done in detail. But for stormwater, for example, it really does almost not exist.” (Interviewee 16)

They attributed this to knowledge gaps concerning stormwater dynamics at sub-catchment level, and treatment facilities at the micro-level, inhibiting the development of clear legislation and guidance. The lack of clear guidelines can act as a barrier to implementing management solutions (Qiao *et al.*, 2019), and there have already been calls for greater coordination at national level (Nykvist, Borgström and Boyd, 2017).

Similar challenges arose due to the shift towards micro-level multifunctional spaces and infrastructures for improving water quality. When considering how to improve nutrient management in the allotments, participants identified uncertainties and knowledge gaps around the state of micro-level drivers like fertilisation rates, cropping and soil management practices and how they were impacting phosphorus dynamics at micro and

sub-catchment level. For example, one interviewee highlighted that knowledge gaps meant that it was currently necessary to scale down knowledge from conventional agriculture:

“There is a lot of knowledge gaps ... and what we are working with is much from like the conventional farming or growing and we try to take those advice that are actually being developed for big scale and scale it down, which is not always so suitable.” (Interviewee 17)

This was seen as an important barrier to strategy development and the same uncertainties appeared around green infrastructures like rain gardens. Rain gardens were seen to balance multiple priorities in one space and as likely to be funded due to their small size. However, several participants stated that knowledge of micro-level hydrological drivers for green infrastructures like rain gardens is currently insufficient for understanding how they function as facilities for phosphorus retention. For example, one interviewee stated:

“About the planting pits, we have to find out how they work over time because I think that if you have a leakage of nutrients you can't... there might be a leakage like the first year and the second year, but what happens after five years or 10 years? We don't know that yet.” (Interviewee 2)

This is an area of ongoing research (Lundy *et al.*, 2022) and collaboration between municipal and academic actors in Stockholm. In this respect, the realities of having to implement multiple goals developed at the national or city sociopolitical levels at the micro-level may have prompted a shift towards technologies whose effectiveness is seen as more uncertain. Consequently, while many participants see developing these types of infrastructures as useful and necessary, this uncertainty creates misalignments with institutional expectations and norms concerning knowledge standards, both within and across sociopolitical levels. Similar misalignments were observed in a case study of blue-green infrastructure implementation in Stockholm, where some actors were reluctant to implement them due to uncertainties around their efficacy (Suleiman, 2021). One outcome was difficulties financing green infrastructures that were intended for nutrient management through stormwater funding schemes. Other authors have highlighted similar difficulties around funding for blue-green solutions (Wihlborg, Sörensen and Alkan Olsson, 2019; Suleiman, 2021).

Suggested changes in norms around knowledge production largely focussed on filling knowledge gaps to reduce uncertainties and create greater alignment with knowledge standards. As argued in the adaptive governance literature (Huitema *et al.*, 2009), monitoring and evaluation were seen as key sociopolitical drivers for enabling implementation by improving knowledge of micro-level hydrological drivers of individual infrastructures, and their impacts on sub-catchment level dynamics over ecologically relevant timeframes. However, several participants encountered difficulties getting funding for monitoring and evaluation over the relevant timeframes. This prevented the knowledge generation and learning that could support appropriate changes in sociopolitical drivers to improve phosphorus management (Nykvist, Borgström and Boyd, 2017). In response, participants saw a need for changes in funding. Further, some participants argued for a shift in norms towards more experimental, ‘learning by doing’ approaches whereby new and “innovative” measures would be implemented despite uncertainties around their efficacy. Space and capacity for experimentation is frequently advocated for in the sustainable management and governance of socioecological systems (Huitema *et al.*, 2009; Bettini *et al.*, 2015; Sandström, Söderberg and Nilsson, 2020). The need for this kind of approach was largely linked to difficulties in evaluating measures when not in-situ and the necessity to develop novel, multi-functional measures. Finally, many participants argued for more collaborative approaches to not only support a shift in norms towards ‘learning-by-doing’, but to address a number of other frictions.

3.3.4 High rate and longevity of change is needed for successful phosphorus management

Temporality played an essential role in the cross-scalar alignments and misalignments, as has been argued in other literature (Cumming, Cumming and Redman, 2006). Interviewees identified two key challenges rooted in the temporal dimensions of hydrological and sociopolitical drivers. The first was how quickly hydrological drivers emerge or change in negative ways, versus the apparent slowness of changes in regulation, behaviour

change and infrastructure. This is a commonly identified cause of mismatches between governance arrangements and the socio-ecological systems (Epstein *et al.*, 2015). As stated by one interviewee:

“So if we are going to have clean water in 2027 -good luck!- we need faster measures because changing people's behaviour, it takes time. And we don't have the time. ... Regulation is the best thing, if you can get it to work.” (Interviewee 6)

Despite the expressed need for changes in regulation and legislation, interviewees were doubtful that national-level legislation would change in the timeframes needed to achieve WFD goals. For example, one interviewee stated that *“the need for revising the legislation in Sweden have been on the agenda for a long time, but it doesn't happen very much,”* (Interviewee 16) which made it challenging to effectively distribute responsibility for water quality measures at the city-level.

The second challenge was how to “keep the flame” burning over the timeframes necessary to achieve ecological change. This means sustaining goals, knowledge, expertise and water quality measures over various sociopolitical cycles, in order to achieve the desired changes in phosphorus dynamics (Folke *et al.*, 2007). There was concern that changes in Sweden’s and Stockholm’s political leadership could lead to the deprioritisation of water quality goals and reduced funding. However, there was also a perception that the WFD and corresponding national-level legislation would be an important driver for maintaining water quality goals over national and city-level political cycles. This issue was also seen as important at the micro-level, as responsibility for managing water quality facilities changes hands. The challenge was described by one interviewee:

“For instance, if you have... rain gardens along the streets, right? You need to explain to the entrepreneurs taking care of it that that you shouldn't put nutrients on it. ... because it's a green factory in disguise, right? It's supposed to retain stuff ... So it's very much like you need to keep the flame and you need to keep the knowledge going.” (Interviewee 12)

It was not only seen as important for water quality goals to be sustained in the long-term, but also the knowledge and expertise needed to maintain measures (Hansen and Pauleit, 2014; Wihlborg, Sörensen and Alkan Olsson, 2019; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020; Suleiman, 2021). This issue was also strongly linked to funding. Several participants stated that facilities need to be maintained, and ideally monitored and evaluated over the timescales needed to see recovery from the ecological impacts of phosphorus over-enrichment. However, there was a perceived lack of funding and resources for maintenance, monitoring and evaluation, resulting in misalignments with ecological timeframes that can act as barriers to effective phosphorus management (Folke *et al.*, 2007; Huitema *et al.*, 2009).

These issues need to be better addressed in approaches to WFD implementation and address concerns over the long-term sustainability of measures for achieving WFD goals. Making funding available for monitoring and maintenance was an important strategy. Participants also suggested implementing educational programmes and making them a requirement of the municipality’s procurement processes, to support the long-term maintenance of knowledge and expertise. Educational programmes were also seen as a way to engage land-users at the micro-level in phosphorus management. In the case of the allotments, this could build on existing educational and environmental certification schemes to support practices that would mitigate phosphorus losses.

3.3.5 Collaboration facilitates implementation through goal integration and multi-functional thinking

Participants saw a need for collaboration and mutual learning across and between sociopolitical levels to address some of the cross-scalar frictions outlined. Both of which have been identified as important for water management that is more aligned with the features of socioecological systems (Pahl-Wostl *et al.*, 2007; Moss, 2012; Glaas, Hjerpe and Jonsson, 2018; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020).

Several interviewees saw collaboration across the city-level as important for achieving goal alignment between the municipal boards and companies that had responsibility for implementing the WFD at sewershed

and sub-catchment level. One interviewee described the logic behind an increase in collaboration around the local action plans:

“But only for the action plans, there has been a collaborative group between the executors and the knowledge producers almost. ... To make sure that everyone is on track with what we are working towards, and that everyone has the knowledge and has the ownership of it.” (Interviewee 3)

Increased collaboration between the municipal boards was seen as a means of increasing the buy-in of the numerous actors at city-level who were needed to implement phosphorus management. Increasing buy-in through collaboration was seen as essential in the absence of city-level legal drivers like legally binding local action plans and has been identified as enabling both the development and implementation of recommendations for watershed management (Koontz and Newig, 2014).

Working collaboratively was presented as essential for enabling the creation of the multi-functional spaces and infrastructures that were deemed necessary for implementing multiple goals in the high-density city. This agrees with findings across relevant literature on urban water issues, and goal integration (Serrao-Neumann *et al.*, 2017; Bohman, Glaas and Karlson, 2020; Kuitert, Willems and Volker, 2023). In the workshops, participants also saw a role for collaboration between municipal and allotment associations at the city-level and individual gardeners at the micro-level to implement pilot projects. Here, collaboration between sociopolitical levels was a way of engaging land-users in producing both knowledge of phosphorus drivers and potential strategies for mitigating losses at this level. One interviewee even suggested that there was a need for new organisations to facilitate collaboration across the city-level. These kinds of organisations, often termed 'bridging organisations' have been identified as important enablers of collaboration and social learning (Pahl-Wostl *et al.*, 2007; Moss, 2012).

4. Conclusions

Phosphorus management and the mitigation of eutrophication are frequently characterised as requiring solutions that are aligned across 'scales' and 'levels'. However, empirical analyses of what this means in practice are relatively scarce. This paper has begun to address this gap by using a transdisciplinary approach to explore the importance of cross-level and cross-scalar dynamics for the downscaling of the WFD, from the perspective of some of the actors involved. We have demonstrated that there is no one level or even scale that can be used in isolation to understand the drivers of phosphorus losses and to develop strategies for their mitigation. Instead, efforts need to be made to understand how parts of the system that are often treated separately interact to enable or inhibit the mitigation of eutrophication.

We show that cross-level analysis can be valuable in contexts where multiple sociopolitical levels are identified as strategically important for phosphorus management. In this case, cross-level analysis identified several misalignments that needed to be addressed to counteract the fragmentation of EU-level WFD goals during the process of downscaling. Clear divisions of responsibility are important for ensuring goal alignment across the relevant sociopolitical levels and can potentially be supported by clear expectations set at national level. Where responsibility for implementation is clearly established, it must be matched by the capacity to achieve coordinated action by relevant actors, particularly when multiple policy goals have the potential to clash. Finding synergies between phosphorus management and other priorities can be of central importance in these cases. However, this is not always possible and novel measures like green infrastructures come with levels of uncertainty that can generate disagreements over their place in nutrient management. Therefore, it is necessary to have appropriate guidance, processes, planning norms and legal powers that ensure the prioritisation of water quality goals in the face of conflicting priorities. In this case study, an important barrier at city-level was the lack of legal weight given to sub-catchment level local action plans, which could only partially be compensated for by enforcement at county-level and the generation of 'buy-in' through collaboration. Another essential enabler is ensuring that available resources match the expectations placed on actors across sociopolitical levels for implementing phosphorus management. In Stockholm, this could mean addressing misalignments between the expectations

placed on the municipal water company for implementing the WFD at sewershed and sub-catchment levels, and the legislation and city-level political decisions that dictate the company's funding streams.

However, cross-level analysis only gives a partial picture that ignores the fundamental role of hydrological drivers in phosphorus dynamics. We demonstrate the utility of cross-scalar analysis by identifying several critical implications of inter-scalar interplay for the implementation of phosphorus management. We determined that responsiveness to sewershed, sub-catchment and micro-level drivers across sociopolitical levels may be important to achieve WFD goals. Including better aligning policy change, funding and the maintenance of goals and expertise to the temporality of hydrological processes. Hydrological drivers across these levels are fundamental for determining what kind of measures can be implemented effectively and where. Therefore, it is important to consider the implications of implementing other policy goals and legislation that can impact relevant hydrological drivers, including land-use and wastewater treatment. Responsiveness to hydrological drivers is inhibited by uncertainties and gaps in knowledge of drivers and processes across hydrological levels. Further, policy goals and legislation originating from multiple levels may either compete with the implementation of water quality measures or drive unfavourable changes to drivers at these levels. In this case study, we identified increasing housing, the reduction of CSOs and the decarbonisation of the wastewater sector as examples of policy goals that could potentially conflict with the mitigation of eutrophication. These are policy goals that have high relevance in many contexts. Critical issues can also arise when hydrological drivers contribute to a significant lack of flexibility in what types of water quality measures can be implemented effectively and where. As demonstrated by this case, high coverage of soils with impervious surfaces at sewershed and sub-catchment levels are key constraints in the urban environment. Under these conditions, if water quality goals are not prioritised highly, the constraints generated by hydrological drivers and competition with other priorities can threaten the achievement of WFD goals. Unfavourable legislation, particularly around land-use and water planning, can pose further problems by undermining coordinated planning and action according to hydrological dynamics.

These findings demonstrate the importance of identifying and addressing cross-level and cross-scalar misalignments for the successfully implementing phosphorus management and addressing the 'wicked problem' of eutrophication. Enhanced cross-level and cross-scalar collaboration can play a central role by facilitating goal alignment or 'buy-in' across levels and scales and filling some important knowledge gaps. Most notably, collaboration can be a way to fill gaps in highly contextual knowledge at the micro-level, and the functioning of novel measures.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Interview Guideline

1. **Can you tell me a bit about your organisation and your role?**
2. **How would you describe your organisation's top 3 goals and priorities with regards to pollution, waste management and green infrastructure?**
 - a. Can you give me some examples of how you're pursuing these goals?
3. **How does the water quality of Stockholm's lakes appear in your priorities?**
 - a. What are forms of pollution are of the greatest concern?
 - b. How would you describe the major sources of phosphorus pollution in Stockholm's lakes?
 - c. Do these differ to sources of nitrogen? How?
 - d. What are the impacts of phosphorus pollution in Stockholm's lakes? Ecologically, socially and economically?
 - e. How does nitrogen contribute?
 - f. How are these impacts assessed?
 - g. How has it impacted your organisation and what you do?
4. **Can you describe the strategies you have in place for reducing the nutrient pollution of Stockholm's lakes?**
 - a. Are nitrogen and phosphorus treated differently? Why?
 - b. Do the strategies also target other or multiple forms of pollution?
 - c. In addition to the strategies you've outlined, what strategies do you have that aim to change the behaviour of individuals or organisations?
 - d. How are these strategies decided upon, implemented and funded?
 - e. Who plays the most important roles?
 - f. Why were these strategies chosen / what were the most important considerations when deciding on strategies / What sources of information are used?
5. **What role do you see for green infrastructure in improving the water quality of Stockholm's lakes?**
 - a. Do you see a role for urban allotments as green infrastructure? Why / why not? How?
6. **How does the idea of 'circularity' appear in your organisation's visions of a sustainable Stockholm?**
 - a. Do you have any strategies that aim to improve the circularity of phosphorus? What are they?
 - b. What about strategies that may indirectly improve the circularity of phosphorus e.g that aim to improve the circularity of the food system?
7. **Can you talk about any barriers you can see to reducing phosphorus pollution in Stockholm's lakes?**
 - a. Challenges around understanding the sources and impacts / choosing measures / implementation and funding / conflicts with other priorities / information?
 - b. What about improving the circularity of phosphorus?
 - c. Do you see any potential synergies between managing phosphorus pollution, improving its circularity and urban gardening?
 - d. What about potential trade-offs?
 - e. How do you think these barriers and trade-offs could be addressed? Are there particular changes you would like to see?

University of Leeds & Linköping University

Urban Agriculture and Phosphorus in Stockholm

Growing practices in gardens and their implications for phosphorus issues in the city

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Introduction

Allotment gardens have existed in Sweden since the late 1800s; the first allotment garden association was established in 1895¹. Currently, there are over 70 allotment garden associations in Stockholm alone and these sites have been highlighted as uniquely important for biodiversity, human health and well-being and education about food production. As a green space, they can also contribute to other sustainability goals in Stockholm; for example, by reducing urban heating, which is increasing due to climate change²⁻⁵.

Figure 1: Urban allotments have a role to play in many of Stockholm's sustainability goals and are included in its biodiversity and food plans.

This also means that waterbodies can't be used for swimming and makes water treatment more difficult and expensive. Therefore, it is important to reduce any losses of phosphorus that might be occurring.

Allotment sites are named as a possible source of phosphorus in the local action plans for Flaten, Kyrksjön, Lillsjön, Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön, Räcksta Träsk and Sicklasjön⁷⁻¹¹, and they may be important in further catchments where they are found. However, there has been little research on this topic¹²⁻¹⁵. Whether, and to what degree, allotment gardens contribute to the amount of phosphorus in a particular waterbody will depend on many different factors. These factors include what stocks of phosphorus are available in soils to be transferred to the lake, the physical proximity of an allotment site to it, and whether the characteristics of the soils and the hydrology of the site favour the transfer of phosphorus to the waterbody. Each of these aspects will be impacted by what allotment gardeners are growing, what they are inputting to the soils and how they manage their gardens. A research team from Linköping University and the University of Leeds in the UK aimed to shed light on some of these factors conducting a case study that focussed on the Johannelund allotment gardens, which are located on the shore of lake Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön.

We investigated 1) how much phosphorus is currently in soils in the Johannelund allotment gardens, and 2) what phosphorus is being added to the gardens, whether it is being added in the form of artificial fertiliser, manure or as compost. An online survey was also distributed to investigate the practices of allotment gardeners more widely, across Stockholm and Sweden. Finally, we ran two workshops with a range of stakeholders to further explore how allotment gardens could play a stronger

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role in the sustainability of Stockholm, focussing on reducing the impact of allotments on nearby water bodies. This report is a preliminary summary of the results of this investigation.

Where did we do our case study?

Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön, shown in **figure 2**, is a bay of lake Mälaren that is divided into three water areas: Bällstaviken-Ulvsundasjön, Karlbergskanalen-Klara sjö and Lillsjön. It is fed by the Bällstaån stream and is connected to the larger lake Mälaren at Mälaren-Riddarfjärden through the canal Karlbergskanalen-Klara sjö in the eastern part of the waterbody and under the Tranebergsbron Bridge in the southern part⁹.

Figure 2: Lake Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön is divided into three water areas: Bällstaviken-Ulvsundasjön, Karlbergskanalen-Klara sjö and Lillsjön. The Johannelund allotment site is highlighted in red.

The responsibility for improving the ecological and chemical status of the waterbody is shared between three municipalities: the City of Stockholm, the City of Solna and the City of Sundbyberg. The catchment is in a metropolitan area, and just under two thirds of its catchment consists of industrial, residential and commercial areas, roadways and car parks. The remaining land area consists of green areas, including forest and sites for allotment gardens⁹.

Johannelund is an allotment site (highlighted in red in **figure 2**) located directly on the banks of Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön. It was established in 1972 on a site that was previously a farm. The allotment site has approximately 122 cultivation lots and no cottages¹⁶.

What Nutrients are Being Added and What is Being Grown?

What is being added to soils in Johannelund?

Nutrients like phosphorus and nitrogen can be added to soils in many forms, including as artificial fertilisers (figure 3), manures, composts or soils. Conversely, nutrients are removed from soils by plants and taken away from allotments in the form of crops like tomatoes, potatoes and kale. If inputs of nutrients to the soils in the allotment site are higher than the nutrient outputs as crops or garden waste this can increase the risk of nutrient losses to nearby waterbodies¹⁷.

Interviews were conducted with 30 allotment gardeners to collect information on what they added to soil, what they grew and how they disposed of organic garden waste^{13,14,18}. The aim of collecting this data was to identify whether current practices in the gardens might increase or decrease the risk of nutrient losses to the nearby waterbody.

Figure 3: An Example of a mineral fertiliser used in the Johannelund allotment site.

Phosphorus inputs mostly come from organic sources. Manure products and added soils are the largest phosphorus source.

Figure 4: The average mass of phosphorus added per m² in 2022, according to input type. This is based on a survey of 30 gardens out of the 122 gardens in Johannelund.

conductor of nutrients, despite having a low nutrient content in comparison to manure, because of the high volume of additional soils that were added. The allotments were also a site for local nutrient

The supply of nutrients to soils came almost entirely from organic inputs like composts and not from artificial fertilisers. This is positive for nutrient recycling and re-use, and the provision of organic matter to the soils. However, it is challenging to balance nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium inputs according to crop needs when solely using organic inputs. A full breakdown of the average inputs of nitrogen, potassium and phosphorus to the 30 gardens surveyed in Johannelund can be seen in appendix 2. Manure and added soil were largest sources of phosphorus to the allotments, as can be seen in figure 4. Added soils were a major

recycling. The gardeners frequently used locally derived nutrient sources like self-made compost, and garden or kitchen ‘wastes’ like grass clippings, wood chips and bokashi.

Nutrient inputs to the allotment gardens were high and were comparable to nutrient inputs found in other research¹³. If nutrient inputs were distributed evenly over the surveyed cultivated area of the allotments, each hectare would receive 1583 kg of nitrogen and 287 kg of phosphorus in the surveyed year. For context, Swedish legislation limits the application of organic fertiliser in agriculture according to its phosphorus content and sets a limit 22 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (as a yearly average over 5 years.) In nitrate vulnerable zones, where there is a bigger risk of negative impacts from added nitrogen, there is also a limit of 170 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ of nitrogen¹⁹. This illustrates the high levels of nutrient inputs to Johannelund. However, there was huge variation in how much nutrients gardeners were inputting to their gardens, as can be seen in **table 1** and **figure 5**.

Table 1: Shows the mean input of nutrients per m² of garden, and the maximum and minimum observed input of nutrients per m² of garden. This shows that the input of nutrients varies greatly between individual plots within Johannelund.

Nutrient	Nitrogen (g/m ²)	Phosphorus (g/m ²)	Potassium (g/m ²)
Mean	168	31	114
Maximum	598	43	110
Minimum	2	0.2	2

The survey also asked gardeners what they grew and in what amounts. Unfortunately, it was not possible to establish nutrient outputs from the collected data as survey respondents generally found it difficult to estimate their harvests. Therefore, it is not possible to estimate what percentage of the nutrients applied to the soil would be taken up by crops. However, we compared the nutrient inputs to the nutrient taken away in the form of crops by an ‘average’ Swedish that was derived from academic literature. This model gave a low nutrient use efficiency where only 2-3% of both the nitrogen and phosphorus added was taken up by plants and removed as crops.

Nutrient inputs vary greatly between different lots within Johannelund.

Figure 5: A whisker box plot showing the variation in the approximate nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium inputs to the cultivated lots. The middle 50% of the samples fall within the range indicated by the coloured box. The central line indicates the median value, while the ‘whisker’ shows the maximum and minimum inputs that were observed.

continuing to build up in the soils of the allotment site. This may

Nutrient inputs are largely organic and the use of artificial fertilisers is uncommon in both Johannelund and across Sweden.

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increase the risk of nutrient losses to the nearby Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön; however, there are a variety of other factors to take into account. These include how water flows through the site (the hydrology), the characteristics of the site soils, and whether there are any practices in the gardens may reduce the risk of phosphorus losses. For example, covering the soil in the winter months can help to reduce soil erosion.

What are allotment gardeners in Sweden growing and using as nutrient inputs?

We distributed an online survey to allotment gardeners across Sweden, in order to understand how Johannelund compared to the rest of Sweden. The survey received 232 responses. The results show that organic inputs are the most commonly used inputs to the gardens, as shown in figure 6, which shows the most popular of 20 surveyed inputs. Again, this is a positive point for nutrient recycling. This is also true at the very local level, as there is re-use of both household and garden waste in the form of grass clippings, self-made compost or bokashi, and leaves. However, it may pose challenges for balancing nutrient inputs for plants, and only 13 respondents (6%) reported using artificial fertilisers.

The survey also showed that allotment gardeners across Sweden, including in Johannelund, are very diverse in terms of what they grow. As can be seen in figure 7, a wide variety of different crops are grown in allotment gardens, with the majority of respondents growing multiple plant species across the surveyed categories. Currently, only 17 respondents (7%) report measuring their harvest in some way. Therefore, quantifying what allotment gardeners are growing in Sweden offers an interesting area of further research that could support a better understanding of nutrient flows in the site.

Allotment gardeners in Johannelund and across Sweden grow a wide variety of different crops in their gardens.

Figure 7: The number of respondents who reported an intention to grow a particular crop in 2022.

Figure 6: The number of survey respondents who reported an intention to use a particular type of input in 2022.

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What is the status of Johannelund's soils?

Soil tests were used to determine phosphorus concentrations in the soil, as well as to evaluate other soil characteristics that can influence phosphorus losses. 11 cultivated lots were sampled, and 3 areas that are currently not being cultivated. A full summary of the results can be found in **appendix 1**. Phosphorus is found in many forms in soils. The majority of the phosphorus in soil is bound to soil particles and is insoluble in water, so it's not readily available for plants to use. However, it may also be converted to water soluble forms of phosphorus over time. This form of phosphorus can be lost to waterbodies through soil erosion. Water soluble forms of phosphorus exist in small amounts in soils and can be taken up by plants. This form of phosphorus can be carried to surface and groundwater dissolved in water, for example, during rainfall or snowmelt. High levels of soil phosphorus increase the risk of phosphorus losses to nearby waterbodies²⁰⁻²².

Soil organic matter content is high in comparison to the average Swedish arable soil.

Figure 9: The range of organic matter % found across the sampled soils.

The soil tests from Johannelund showed very high levels of phosphorus in soils taken from the cultivated lots. The average concentration of plant available phosphorus concentration was 52 mg/100g of soil. For context, the generally recommended optimum for maintaining crop yields in conventional Swedish agriculture is 4-10 mg/ 100g. This is class III to a class IV, as shown in green, in **figure 8**²³. The phosphorus

Phosphorus levels in both the cultivated and uncultivated areas that were sampled are higher than the agronomic optimum.

Figure 8: The range of plant available phosphorus concentrations found in the sampled soils. The classes shown on the chart are used to indicate whether the phosphorus concentration would be considered below the agronomic optimum (class I – II), approximately optimal (class III – IV), or above the optimum (class V).

levels in the uncultivated areas were also high, which suggests that the history of the site may have played an important role in establishing current phosphorus levels. The levels of phosphorus in the allotment garden soils are much higher than the recommended optimum. This represents a significant stock of phosphorus that could potentially be transported to the nearby waterbody^{21,22}.

The pH of the sampled soils ranged from pH 5.9 to pH 7.1, with an average pH of 6.6. Average soil organic matter for the cultivated areas was 12%, while the uncultivated areas had an average of 10%.

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(figure 9) This is higher than the typical Swedish arable soils, which have an organic matter content of around 4%²⁴. Higher soil organic matter is positively associated with soil productivity and carbon sequestration. Furthermore, it can reduce the risk of soil losses from erosion by encouraging the formation of soil aggregates. However, high levels of soil organic matter may also increase phosphorus availability and, subsequently, dissolved phosphorus losses²⁵.

How can allotment gardens play a role in a sustainable Stockholm? What we learned from the workshops

Participants in the 2 workshops had slightly different visions of how allotments could be made more sustainable or play a greater role in the sustainability of the city.

Participants in both workshops highlighted the need for allotments sites to improve the sustainability of water use, fertilisation practices and stormwater management. In the 2nd workshop, they also saw a need to reduce inputs like peat, plastics and toxic substances to the allotment gardens. This was not just a way to improve the sustainability of the allotments, but also to protect the allotment sites themselves from negative impacts. In this respect, the workshop participants all saw areas where allotment sites could improve the sustainability of certain practices. However, they also saw areas where the allotments could actively contribute to the sustainability of the city overall. Participants in both workshops saw allotments as potentially important sites for the local recycling of organic waste. In the 2nd workshop the participants also saw allotments as contributing to both biodiversity and social sustainability in Stockholm. Participants in the 2nd workshop saw higher numbers of allotment sites as positive for the sustainability of the city overall.

While different perspectives emerged in the two workshops, the visions were more similar than they were different. Taken together, the following vision of a sustainable allotment site emerged: a sustainable allotment site is one that contributes to community and social cohesion, biodiversity and the health of pollinators, and the local re-use of organic materials. Water, nutrients and other inputs are used responsibly for cultivation, and stormwater is managed to protect nearby waterbodies from nutrient losses.

What actions could be taken to achieve this goal?

In both workshops, a wide variety of actions were suggested that could improve the role that allotment sites play in the sustainability of Stockholm. The suggested actions centred around 5 key themes: information, collaboration, clear expectations, and changes in practices and spaces.

The participants in both workshops saw an important role for governmental bodies and for the allotment garden associations in providing a variety of information to the allotment gardeners. In both workshops governmental bodies were to provide data and research on the water quality of the local waterbodies. Furthermore, the allotment garden associations and, in the 1st workshop, the governmental bodies were to provide information that would support specific changes in practices. The information to be provided included information on better cultivation methods, improving nutrient management, composting, and the use of cover crops. Collaboration between the allotment gardens, the city, and other actors within the city was important for facilitating the recycling of organic waste. It was also suggested that collaboration should play a greater role in the development of regulations and defining how spaces in the city should be used. In both workshops, participants saw a need for clear expectations and regulations on how allotment spaces should be used. A key action was putting stipulations concerning how waste, water, invasive species and nutrients are managed in the allotment gardens into the lease agreement between the city and the allotment gardens. It was also suggested that improvements in nutrient management could be supported by creating better regulations on the

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contents of fertiliser products. The final group of actions focussed on the changes in practices in the allotment gardens and in the space itself. Participants in both the 1st and the 2nd workshop suggested that facilities for stormwater management could be introduced. Participants in the 2nd workshop suggested a wide range of actions that could be taken by the allotment gardeners to make their practice more sustainable. These included producing of compost, cultivating green manures, changing the timing of water use and introducing cover cropping to reduce water loss. Other suggested actions were growing plants that were attractive to pollinators, and to change the culture behind growing towards more holistic practices like permaculture. Governmental bodies also had an important role to play by providing support to make any desired changes possible.

What did we learn and where do we need more research?

Soil analyses and the calculation of nutrient inputs to the site indicate that there is a risk that phosphorus (and other nutrients) may be transported from the allotment site to the nearby waterbody. There are currently high levels of phosphorus in the soils, which means that there is a significant stock of phosphorus that may be transferred to the nearby waterbody under the right conditions. Furthermore, there are continuing high inputs of nutrients that are likely in excess of plant needs. Adding an excess of phosphorus will mean further build-up of this nutrient in the soil, which can increase the risk of phosphorus transfer to the lake.

We have established that there is a stock of phosphorus in the allotment gardens that is likely increasing. However, this topic needs further investigation before any conclusions may be drawn about relative contribution of allotment sites to phosphorus levels in Mälaren-Ulvsundasjön. It was not possible to establish nutrient outputs from the collected data, as many allotment gardeners did not record their harvest and found it difficult to estimate. Therefore, it is not possible to properly assess how much of the applied nutrients is actually being taken up by plants versus what is building up in the soil. Furthermore, the potential for phosphorus losses doesn't necessarily mean that there are significant phosphorus losses from the site: this will depend on the features of the soil, the hydrology of the site and the soil management practices of the gardeners. The extremely close proximity of the allotment site to the lake suggests that they are hydrologically connected; nevertheless, further work needs to be done to characterise the hydrology of the site before the role of the allotment site in phosphorus flows in the catchment can be established.

In the workshops the participants outlined a number of ways that the allotments could be made more sustainable or play a greater role in a sustainable Stockholm. The sites have the potential to improve community and social cohesion, biodiversity and the health of pollinators, and the local re-use of organic materials in Stockholm. However, they must use water, nutrients and other responsibly for cultivation, and manage any stormwater to protect nearby waterbodies from nutrient losses. The participants identified 4 main actions that should be taken to achieve this goal: 1) Governmental bodies and the allotment associations should provide information to improve awareness and support changes in practices, 2) The municipal government and the allotment associations should collaborate to develop local recycling of organic matter and to support more democratic decision-making concerning the uses of space, 3) They should also outline clear expectations and regulations around how allotment sites should be used in sustainable ways, and 4) In the gardens there should be changes in practices and the introduction of stormwater management, supported by the municipality.

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Appendix 1: Table of soil test results from Johannelund allotment site

Table 2: The soil test results from the 11 gardens (note the lot numbers in the table are randomly assigned) and 3 uncultivated areas that were sampled. Ler, silt and sand are the different particle sizes of weathered rock that make up soils. The smallest particle size, ler, is particularly important for holding water and nutrients. Mull is the part of the soil that is made up of organic matter and also plays a key role in water and nutrient retention. "AL" refers to ammonium lactate extraction, which is the method used to extract the different nutrients from the soil. This test is used to estimate what phosphorus (P), potassium (K), magnesium (Mg) and Calcium (Ca) is in the soil that is relatively accessible by plants. The ratio of potassium to magnesium is important for their efficient uptake. The maximum recommended ratio varies by K-AL class but is between 2.5 (class I-II) and 1.5 (class IV – V). The classes given for phosphorus and potassium are used to tailor fertiliser recommendations in conventional agriculture based on what nutrients are already in the soil. In the case of phosphorus, a class III – IV would be approximately optimal depending on crop P demand, while a class V would be above the optimum. Aluminium (Al) and iron (Fe) are important for binding phosphorus in soils. So, Al-AL and Fe-AL can be used to indicate whether soils have a low capacity to absorb more phosphorus and may present a risk of leaching losses.²⁶

Lott	pH ¹	P-AL mg/100g	Klass	K-AL mg/100g	Klass	Mg-AL mg/100g	K/Mg-AL	Ca-AL mg/100g	Al-AL mg/100g	Fe-AL mg/100g	Mull %	Ler %	Silt %	Sand %
Lott 1	5.9	41.1	V	32.5	V	27.9	1.2	338	26	35	6.9	23	43	27
Lott 2	6.8	81.3	V	52.2	V	55.1	0.9	624	19	39	10.5	13	39	38
Lott 3	6.8	52.3	V	39.5	V	42.6	0.9	513	23	40	8.8	23	40	28
Lott 4	7.0	62.8	V	28.2	IV	58.0	0.5	816	42	25	20.4	14	35	31
Lott 5	6.5	74.7	V	44.8	V	44.3	1.0	540	23	31	11.8	17	44	27
Lott 6	6.4	58.3	V	36.9	V	44.8	0.8	550	18	23	18.4	11	32	39
Lott 7	6.4	43.1	V	27.8	IV	31.1	0.9	404	19	31	6.9	27	37	29
Lott 8	7.0	50.2	V	44.2	V	43.9	1.0	588	19	51	13.2	19	40	28
Lott 9	7.1	53.4	V	32.9	V	48.5	0.7	576	17	26	11.6	17	42	30
Lott 10	6.6	18.2	V	21.3	IV	48.8	0.4	433	18	54	13.5	23	40	24
Lott 11	6.7	19.4	V	20.5	IV	35.5	0.6	358	16	30	5.5	28	44	23
Bakgrund 1	6.6	37.3	V	53.7	V	42.2	1.3	565	16	58	15.3	13	40	32
Bakgrund 2	6.3	19.1	V	50.6	V	30.4	1.7	336	20	37	6.7	21	46	26
Bakgrund 3	6.3	35.5	V	58.1	V	36.9	1.6	385	17	30	9.0	21	47	24

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Appendix 2: The phosphorus, nitrogen and potassium inputs per m², by input type for the surveyed gardens in Johannelund. This was calculated by dividing the total inputs to the gardens by the area of the cultivated lots. In reality, inputs are not evenly distributed across the cultivated area.

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Appendix 3: Mental model ‘factors’ (these were supplied in Swedish)

Factor	Definition	Factor	Definition
 Access to information	The existence of and access to knowledge, or the means to investigate questions.		
 Monitoring schemes	Data collection and sharing on relevant topics.		
 Pilot areas / project	The capacity to test new ways of doing things and assess their impacts.		
 Waste management	Handling of waste of biological origin both in and outside of gardens.		
 Food production	Availability of edible plants.		
 Civic participation	The ability to play a role in addressing public concerns through access to people and resources in government.		
 Water quality	The cleanliness of the water and how it impacts its use for leisure, drinking water and as a habitat.		

Appendix 4: Workshop exercises (these were supplied in Swedish)

Exercise 1 Instructions for Participants

What are mental models?

1. Mental models are our personal understandings of the world around us, how things are and how they work.
2. This exercise asks you to explore and communicate how you perceive urban allotments, water quality, urban sustainability, and the relationships between them.
3. The mental models will be made up of 'factors', which are elements that you think can affect how urban allotments and water quality impact each other and the role they play in urban sustainability. They will also show relationships between the factors, which indicate how you think different factors can impact each other and how strong this impact is.

How to do the mental modelling exercise

1. Choose or draw factors: identify factors that you think are related to urban allotments, water quality and the relationship between them.
2. Select factors from those given.
3. You may also write up to 3 of your own.
4. Stick them to the sheet given to you.
5. Show relationships with arrows: Join the factors with arrows to show the relationship between them and the direction of the relationship.
6. Use the arrows given or draw them in black.
7. Think about what the relationship is.
8. Indicate the strength of the relationship by choosing or drawing thicker arrows for stronger relationships.

Key questions to consider

1. What factors affect the relationship between urban allotments, water quality and urban sustainability?
2. How can urban allotments impact, or be impacted by water quality?
3. What factors can impact these relationships?

Exercise 2 Instructions for Participants

Key Question

What actions should be taken to improve the ability of urban allotments to reduce nutrient use and loss, and play a greater role in urban sustainability?

How to do the exercise

There will be **3 rounds** to this exercise where you will be asked to identify which **actors** can impact different **factors**, and the **actions** they should take to improve the ability of urban allotments to reduce nutrient use and loss, and to play a greater role in urban sustainability.

Round 1: What factors can your organisation directly impact and what actions should they take?

1. **Identify factors** that your organisation can impact.
2. **On blue sticky 'action' cards**, write the name of your organisation and the action they should take.
3. Present your actions to the group and stick them to the sheet.
4. Link the action to the factor it can impact using pen.

Round 2: What actions should other actors take?

1. **Identify actors** that can impact the factors on the sheet or are needed to facilitate the actions that have already been identified.
2. **On purple sticky 'action' cards**, write the name of the actor and the action they should take.
3. Present them to the group and stick them to the sheet.
4. Link the action to the factor or existing action it can impact using pen.

Round 3: As a group, select 5 actions that you think will be the most beneficial.